

Announcement

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16th Annual Medicinal & Pharmaceutical Sciences Congress

Seoul, South Korea

October 16-17, 2017

<http://medpharma.pharmaceuticalconferences.com/>

**Med Pharma
Congress**

Dear Colleagues,

Conference Series LLC is delighted to welcome you to Seoul, South Korea for the prestigious **16th Annual Medicinal & Pharmaceutical Sciences Congress** on **October 16-17, 2017** at **Seoul, South Korea. Med Pharma Congress** will focus on the theme **“Developing the Synergy between Pharmaceuticals and Medicinal Chemistry to Deliver Better Drugs”**. We are confident that you will enjoy the Scientific Program of this upcoming Conference.

We look forward to see you at Seoul, South Korea.

With Regards,
Med Pharma Congress Operating Committee
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Program Announcement

Accommodation

A large number of rooms have been reserved. Discounted room rates for Med Pharma Congress participants are proposed. Only reservations made through the Conference will benefit these rates. The Congress Center can be easily reached by Public transportation.

Exhibition and Sponsorship

An Exhibition will be held concurrently with the Congress. The coffee break and lunch areas will be located adjacent to the booths. Thanks to exhibitors from all over the world, attendees will have a complete overview of new findings in the fields of Polymer Science.

About Seoul

Seoul, the capital of South Korea, is a colossal city where cutting edge high rises and neon lights to Buddhist sanctuaries, royal residences and pagodas, Seoul is a captivating blend of old and new. A center point of business, culture and back both inside South Korea and globally, Seoul houses the base camp for a portion of the world's biggest organizations. It likewise has one of the world's best tram frameworks – the most straightforward approach to get around in this thickly populated range. For the best perspective of the city, go to the tower on Namsan, one of the mountains that encompass the city. Seoul is viewed as a main and rising worldwide city. Seoul is encompassed by mountains, the tallest being Mt. Bukhan, the world's most went by national park per square foot. Present day points of interest incorporate the famous N Seoul Tower, the gold-clad 63 Building, the neofuturistic Dongdaemun Design Plaza, Lotte World, the world's second biggest indoor amusement park, Moonlight Rainbow Fountain, the world's longest extension wellspring and the Sevit Floating Islands. Soul is the world's ninth most gone to city and fourth biggest worker in tourism. Remarkable attractions incorporate advanced Dongdaemun Design Plaza, a tradition lobby with bending engineering and a housetop park; Gyeongbokgung Palace and Jogyesa Temple.

Venue

Seoul, South Korea

Important Dates

Abstract Submission Opens : October 25, 2016

Online Registration Opens : October 25, 2016

Early bird registration : March 28, 2017

On Spot Registration : October 16, 2017

Conference Secretariat

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